

Assess the Level of Knowledge Regarding Hospital Emergency Codes among Staff Nurses

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Abstract

Emergency codes warn healthcare staff during an emergency while additionally scaring patients or visitors. When a code is called, a pre-designated team of doctors, nurses, and other professionals react quickly and efficiently, according to learning. Nurses must empower themselves to enable them to function effectively, amid hospital emergency codes. Aim of the study is to evaluate the knowledge level on hospital emergency codes. To determine the relationship between the demographic variables and the knowledge level. Research approach and design was utilized is quantitative, Non-experimental methods -univariate descriptive design. The purposive sampling approach was used for a sample size among 100 staff nurses, to figure out the degree of competence regarding hospital emergency codes with a structured knowledge questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistics analysis was adopted. The p-value was <0.001 indicating statistically significant. Findings indicate that knowledge enhancements are linked to improve responses can be impact hospital emergency codes outcome.

Introduction

The notion of "emergency" denotes an event. This expression refers to a managerial aspect that concede for resolution and implementing certain actions A designated individual must impose or declare an "emergency state," and they will eventually lift it as well. It therefore necessitates the identification of threshold values and implies participation guidelines as well as a departure strategy. It conceptually relates to response and is typically used to define time and space. Life-threatening circumstances can happen to anybody, anywhere, at any time. In the final phase, the doctor, nurse and multidisciplinary team has to effectively manage the emergency circumstances. Lack of training may lead one to be unprepared for medical emergencies, poses operational risks and even legal repercussions [1,2]. In order to address medical emergencies, healthcare providers must be well-prepared. To handle various situations quickly and

effectively, hospitals need to be fully stocked with medications and supplies.

There is variability between hospitals after these standards of protocols are in place separately by each hospital. Healthcare professionals have in the past encountered misunderstanding at crucial times due to this practice [1–5]. Healthcare professionals may work at several medical centres and move between them regularly, which makes it difficult for them to remember and react to the appropriate code when it's needed.

Any circumstance, whether man-made or natural, that calls for quick, decisive action to save lives or property is considered an emergency. As a result, reacting to an emergency needs to be done swiftly, carefully, and systematically. An incident sparked the first attempts to standardize emergency codes in hospitals.

Need for the Study

In an emergency, nurses are the ones who save lives, so it is important for them to be knowledgeable about

More Information

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hospital emergency codes. The disciplined handling of risk and risk avoidance is the simplest definition of emergency code management. The likelihood of survival is increased by prompt emergency management and early identification. In hospitals, nurses serve as the primary triage anchors. Medical emergency codes are applied uniformly in the global to notify staff members of different medical emergencies. The intent of using codes is to reduce stress and fear in hospital visitors while expeditiously communicating vital information to medical workers with the limited confusion. Clinical nurses who were more adept at recognizing emergency codes also had better levels of competence and confidence.

In July 2019, a descriptive design was executed at St James Hospital in Chalakudy to evaluate staff nurses' awareness of the hospital emergency code. There were sixty staff nurses included in the trial. According to the report, 11.6% of Nurses are enlightened with the hospital emergency code. Additionally, the data showed a substantial correlation between the total number of years of experience and knowledge level, but not between age and certification.

A descriptive study on Korean hospital staff members' opinions about hospital emergency colour codes. An extent of 295 questionnaires were distributed and 266 of them were evaluated between October 25 and November 30, 2016. The findings demonstrated the highest degree of consistency between emergency code colour images and colour images related to emergencies in the following scenarios: "black for violent/combatative person," "red for fire," "blue for adult cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR)," "yellow for paediatric CPR," "orange for external disaster," "pink for infant/child abduction," "white for deactivation," and "blue for fire." In the meantime, purple, grey, and silver were the most perplexing hues. Hospital employees typically choose colours that correspond to the emergency codes used at those facilities.

In an emergency, a nurse is the one who saves a life, hence it is her responsibility to educate oneself about hospital emergency codes. The likelihood of survival may be increased by prompt emergency management and early identification. The investigator evaluates the understanding of emergency codes. This study employed a qualitative pre-experimental one group pre-test & post-test research design. The Holy Cross College of Nursing in Kottayam's second-year BSc nursing students provided the data. Convenience sampling was used to choose the 48 Total samples. Second-year BSc nursing students' knowledge of emergency codes was evaluated using a standardized knowledge assessment tool, and a structured training program intervention was provided right after the pre-test. The post-test was completed on the day of the intervention. For analysis, both descriptive and

inferential statistics were employed. Pre-test mean scores were 8.40, while post-test mean scores were 19. Following the intervention, the researcher discovered a discrepancy that is statistically significant in nursing students' average awareness of emergency codes ($p < 0.001$). Thus, the study came to the conclusion that a structured training approach was useful in improving the second-year BSc nursing students' understanding of emergency codes.

An essential component in hospital settings is the hospital emergency code. As researchers, we discovered that hospitals desperately needed hospital emergency codes in order to give patients prompt interventions. We can determine a student nurse's capacity to assist and support staff nurses in an emergency by examining their familiarity with hospital emergency codes. Therefore, it is Significant to conduct research on hospital emergency codes integrated to be ready to handle emergency situations and to offer prompt aid. The study's goal was to evaluate hospitals' emergency preparedness and response capacity in relation to the variation in emergency codes and alerts used in hospital emergency situations.

Statement of the Problem

A Descriptive Study to assess the level of knowledge on Hospital Emergency Codes among staff Nurses in MGMCR&RI at Puducherry.

Objectives

1. To assess the level of knowledge on hospital emergency codes among Staff Nurses in MGMCR&RI at Puducherry.
2. To find out association between levels of knowledge on hospital emergency codes with the selected demographic variables of Staff Nurses in MGMCR&RI at Puducherry.

Operational Definitions

Assess

The investigation seeks to elucidate the benefits of hospital emergency codes among staff nurses at MGMCR&RI in Puducherry by employing a structured knowledge questionnaire to gauge their degree of understanding.

Knowledge

The investigator designed a systematic knowledge questionnaire to test knowledge, which is defined as the understanding of information abilities related to hospital emergency codes and emergency code management.

Hospital emergency codes

An emergency code is a notification of an event that requires immediate action. Preparing for the Unexpected Emergencies can strike anywhere and at any time. In the spirit of proactively we encourage you to have your own emergency preparedness plan.

Staff nurses

A nurse provides independent and team-based care to people of all ages, in all situations, for families, groups, and communities, whether they are ill or not. The fields of nursing include illness prevention, health promotion, and the care of the sick, disabled, and dying. Other important nursing responsibilities include research, education, patient and health systems management, advocacy, and the creation of a safe environment.

Hypotheses

H₁: There is a relationship between certain demographic characteristics and staff nurses' degree of awareness regarding hospital emergency codes.

Assumptions

- Majority of staff nurses are working in general wards and OPD's are having less competence on Hospital emergency codes.
- Information booklet is an effective way to improve the insight on Hospital emergency codes among staff nurses.

Material and Methods

Design

The present study employs a quantitative research plan, utilizing a quantitative non-experimental univariate descriptive design as its research design.

Figure 1: A Schematic Depiction of the Research Design

Key: O1 - Assessment of knowledge level on Hospital emergency codes

The study's context was conducted in MGMCRI at Puducherry Using the Samples' availability and close vicinity, the study was set up. The samples believe in holistic care and determined to provide the same to their clients. The nurses work cautiously and continuously for the welfare of the clients who are admitted in MGMCRI even in the clients least possibility of survival chance. Therefore, regardless of where they are posted in general wards or outpatient departments, this study will benefit a wide spectrum of staff nurses.

Participants

Population of this study consists among 100 staff nurses in MGMCRI at Puducherry.

Sample & Sample Size

The sample of the study was staff nurses; 100 staff nurses at the MGMCRI in Puducherry were chosen as the study's sample size. Technique for sampling: Purposive sampling was used to select samples from the accessible population of staff nurses at MGMCRI who met the inclusion criteria.

Data collection procedure

Development and description of tool; the tools consist of two sections

- Section A: Socio- Demographic variables of participant.
- Section B: Structured knowledge Questionnaire on Hospital Emergency Codes

Section A :(socio- demographic variables)

The demographic variables include Age, Religion, Gender, Marital status, Basic education, Years of experience, Ever heard of Hospital emergency codes, Perceived Importance of Hospital Emergency Codes Management, Have you witnessed Hospital Emergency Codes Management programme, Are you a member of Hospital Emergency Codes Management.

Section B: Structured knowledge Questionnaire (30 questions) on Hospital Emergency Codes

The assessment of knowledge level indicates to know about the Hospital Emergency Codes in staff nurses. How the nurse is identifying their conflict and crisis situation how they are managing to save the life of patient during emergency. The knowledge questionnaire contains 30 questions with choice so staff nurses can be able to pick up their individual answers to identify the competence level on Hospital Emergency Codes.

Data collection method

Verbal informed consent was received from the research subjects. Participants' information was gathered using a demographic tool and structured knowledge questionnaire. Employee nurses received a brochure about hospital emergency codes.

Following the researcher's self-introduction, the staff nurses were educated about the study protocol and asked for their informed oral consent if they would like to participate. Fewer than five years of experience as staff nurses. From general wards and OPDs, 100 samples were collected.

A systematic knowledge questionnaire and the interview approach was adopted to gather the information and to evaluate the pre-test level of knowledge on hospital emergency codes. Staff nurses received a handbook on emergency codes at the conclusion of the trial.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of general profile the level of knowledge on Hospital Emergency Codes among staff nurses in MGMCRI

N=100

S.no	Demographic variables	n	%
1.	Age in year's		
	a. 18-25 years	53	53
	b. 26-30 years	29	29
	c. 31-40 years	18	18
2.	Religion		
	a. Hindu	49	49
	b. Muslim	18	18
	c. Christian	33	33
3.	Sex		
	a. Male	30	30
	b. Female	70	70
	Marital status		
4.	a. Married	28	28
	b. unmarried	72	72
5.	Basic qualification		
	a. ANM	8	8
	b. GNM	10	10
	c. B.Sc Nursing	58	58
6.	Year of experience		
	a. Fresher	23	23
	b. 1- 5 years	45	45
	c. >5years	22	22
7.	Ever heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management		
	a. Yes	85	85
	b. No	15	15
	Perceived Importance of Hospital Emergency Codes Management		
8.	a. Yes	28	28
	b. No	72	72
9.	Have you witnessed Hospital Emergency Codes Management programme		
	a. Yes	12	12
	b. No	88	88
	Are you a member of Hospital Emergency Codes Management		
10.	a. Yes	0	0
	b. No	100	100

Table 1: It represents demographic characteristics of staff nurses regarding Hospital Emergency Codes Figure 1: Display the knowledge distribution of staff nurses regarding hospital emergency codes. Out of 100 staff nurses, 14 % had sufficient knowledge, 30 % had somewhat adequate knowledge, and 56 % had poor knowledge.

An association knowledge level on hospital emergency codes with the selected demographic characteristics among staff nurses in MGMCRI. The data revealed with

regard to the demographic characteristics, Evidence showed that notable association seen in the variables of Staff nurse Sex, Ever heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management. Empirical evidence from staff nurse assessment of Sex is <0.031, ever heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management is <0.029. It was significant at p<0.05 level. Thus, it was concluded that a strong correlation existed between Staff nurse Sex, Ever heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management.

Figure 1: Percentage Distribution Level of Knowledge on Hospital Emergency Codes among Staff Nurses

Results

Analysis strategies

1. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in the data analysis due to the study's objectives.
2. The level of hospital emergency code awareness among staff nurses and a chosen demographic parameter would be correlated using the Chi-square test.

The study's findings were divided into the following sections:

Section A

The general profile's frequency and percentage distribution reveal how proficient the staff nurses at MGMCRI are in hospital emergency codes.

Section B

The frequency and percentage distribution to gauge the staff nurses' knowledge of hospital emergency codes at MGMCRI.

Section C

The relationship between the staff nurses' level of understanding of hospital emergency codes and the chosen demographic variables is discussed

Discussion

The current study's primary goal was to gauge staff nurses' familiarity with hospital emergency codes at MGMCRI in Puducherry.

The first step is to evaluate staff nurses' understanding of Hospital Emergency Codes and their results. According to data, the majority of staff nurses had knowledge that was either poor or somewhat adequate, while very few had adequate knowledge. It displays the staff nurses' knowledge distribution regarding hospital emergency codes. Among 100 Staff nurses, 14% have sufficient knowledge, 30 % had

somewhat enough knowledge, and 56 % lacked sufficient understanding.

Finding a relationship between the staff nurses' degree of understanding of hospital emergency codes and the chosen demographic characteristics at MGMCRI in Puducherry was the study's second goal.

Shows the association knowledge level on hospital emergency codes with the selected demographic characteristics of staff nurses in MGMCRI. According to the data, there was a substantial correlation between the demographic factors of staff nurse sex and ever having heard of hospital emergency codes management. The test result that was acquired from Staff nurse Sex is $p < 0.031$ ever heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management is $p < 0.029$. It was significant at $p < 0.05$ level. Thus, it was concluded that Staff Nurse Sex and Ever Heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management were significantly correlated.

Hence the stated Hypothesis H₁ There was an association between the level of knowledge on hospital emergency codes outcome with Staff nurse Sex, Ever heard of Hospital Emergency Codes Management among staff nurses was accepted.

Conclusion

The primary objective of the study was to evaluate the staff nurses' knowledge of hospital emergency codes at MGMCRI in Puducherry. Specialists assessed the tool's content validity. MGMCRI staff nurses provided formal oral consent. The split half method was applied to ascertain reliability, and if necessary, appropriate alterations were made. Information was acquired from staff nurses at Puducherry's MGMCRI over a one-week data collection session. The MGMCRI served as the study's location. To assess the study hypothesis and determine whether the variables had a relationship, and the acquired data was examined using both

descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage) and inferential statistics (Wilcoxon Signed Rank test and Pearson Chi-Square test).

The researcher encountered challenges in gathering data because of the regular schedule of staff nurses, given that The research was centered on the prevalence of information related hospital emergency codes.

The goal of this research was to gauge participants' familiarity with hospital emergency codes. Delaying the activation of emergency codes to save patient lives is a common practice among staff nurses. Because of this, the investigation shows to evaluate their level of awareness regarding the activation of emergency codes in wards.

Recommendations

The study's conclusions led to the following recommendations for additional research:

Research can be done to evaluate staff nurses' ability to manage. A research on how other medical professionals handle emergency situations may be carried out. Regular Drills and Training: Conduct regular emergency code drills and training sessions.

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Author Contribution

Mrs. Nithyapriya R.: Conceptualization of the study, formulation of research questions, and methodology design.

Mrs. Rajaveni P.: Data collection, coordination with hospital staff, and administration of the knowledge assessment. Data analysis, interpretation of results, and statistical calculations.

Mrs. Nithyapriya R.: Writing of the manuscript draft, literature review, and manuscript editing.

Prof. Geetha C.: Final review of the manuscript, approval of the final version for submission, and supervision of the overall project.

Funding Statement

No funding was provided for this investigation

Competing Interest

Hospital emergency codes are critical for ensuring timely and effective responses to medical emergencies. Codes may not be effectively communicated to staff or patients. Addressing these gaps through targeted training, multilingual support, and resource enhancement can improve patient safety, staff confidence, and community trust. In the realm of nursing, the study's conclusions are applicable in practice. The authors declare that they have no competing interests related to this study. No evidence of any conflict towards to this investigation.

Ethical Clearance

Every procedure in this investigation complied with equivalent ethical standards or the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its revisions. "The ethical aspect of the study has been institutionally reviewed". Informed consent has been procured by all respondents in this study.

References

- [1] Lilly S. A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding emergency triage among student nurses in selected institutions, Jalandhar.
- [2] Saxena D, Takhelchangbam N, Agarwal T, Kumar B, NP S, PK J. Knowledge and awareness regarding emergency colour codes among resident doctors and nursing staffs of tertiary care facility of district Etawah. *Int J Healthc Educ Med Inform.* 2021;8(1):12–18. doi: 10.24321/2455.9199.202109
- [3] Nandini. Hospital emergency codes. *Int J Nurs Educ Res.* 2020;8(3):415–8. doi: 10.5958/2454-2660.2020.00092.7
- [4] Nanthini D, Nivetha G, Rajeswari S. A comparative study to assess the knowledge on code blue protocol among the nurses of general ward and critical care unit at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute, Puducherry, India. *Pondicherry J Nurs.* 2019;12(1):1–4. doi: 10.5005/jp-journals-10084-12106
- [5] Padilla-Elías N, Peña-Orellana M, Rivera-Gutiérrez R, González-Sánchez JA, Centeno HAM, Alonso-Serra H, et al. Diversity of emergency codes in hospitals. *Int J Clin Med.* 2013;4(11):608–13. doi: 10.4236/ijcm.2013.411088
- [6] Thomas N, Karunanidhi Devi W. A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding triage among staff nurses of Batra Hospital and Medical Research Centre [BHMRC], New Delhi. *Int J Sci Healthc Res.* 2024;9(1):114–9. doi: 10.52403/ijshr.20240115
- [7] Wandile BV, Kanyal D. Knowledge of emergency colour codes among healthcare workers in a tertiary care hospital of Wardha, Maharashtra, India: A cross-sectional study. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2023;17(2):10–13. doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2023/58898.18290
- [8] Variability of emergency color codes for critical events between hospitals in Riyadh [Internet]. [cited 2024 Sep 20]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6074476/>
- [9] Department of Community Medicine, UPUMS, Saifai, Etawah, Uttar Pradesh, India. Knowledge and awareness regarding emergency colour codes among resident doctors and nursing staffs of tertiary care facility of district Etawah. *Int J Healthc Educ Med*

Inform. 2021;8(1):12–18. doi:
10.24321/2455.9199.202109
[10] International Journal of Advances in Nursing
Management. A study to assess the level of knowledge
and attitude regarding expression and storage of breast

milk among lactating mothers at Pondicherry Institute
of Medical Sciences, Puducherry [Internet]. [cited 2024
Sep 20]. Available from:
[https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:
ijanm&volume=8&issue=1&article=018](https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ijanm&volume=8&issue=1&article=018)

